

FACTORS AFFECTING THE INTENTION TO PIRATE SOFTWARE PRODUCTS AMONG UNDERGRADUATES

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Introduction

Software piracy is a computer crime that was expedited by the rapid advancements in technology (Chan, Ma and Wong, 2013). It is a form of digital piracy that is defined as the illegal copying, distribution and use of licensed software without the consent or knowledge of the software creators or owners (Lau, 2007). Software pirates are sanctioned under the Copyright Law in most countries, including Sri Lanka since software piracy is considered a criminal activity. Developed countries view software piracy as an immoral act, while developing countries have an opposite view towards it (Arli and Tjiptono, 2016).

Previous studies have investigated factors affecting software piracy intention in several aspects such as ethical, behavioural, socio-psychological, and legal. Most of these studies have utilized the Theory of Planned Behaviour (TPB) and General Ethics Theory to identify factors under each of these aspects (Arli and Tjiptono, 2016; Jaafar, Ramayah and Teng, 2008; Yoon, 2011). According to Lau (2007) and Rishi and Mehra (2017), people engage in piracy activities, ignoring the legal consequences of such engagement. Further, previous studies found that the unaffordability of licensed software attracts individuals to copy, download and use them illegally (Jaafar, Ramayah and Teng, 2008).

Munasinghe and Pemarathna (2017) found that undergraduates do not view software piracy as a harmful activity. This finding was inconsistent with other studies where Moral Obligation was a significant factor affecting intention (Arli and Tjiptono, 2016; Jaafar, Ramayah and Teng, 2008). Many

studies have incorporated factors in TPB: attitude, perceived behavioural control and subjective norms to investigate software piracy intention (Arlı and Tjiptono, 2016; Phau and Ng, 2010; Yoon, 2011). However, previous studies provided inconsistent results when considering the variables that are commonly used in them. Further, most of the studies were from countries in western and south-east regions which caused issues in generalizing the findings to the Sri Lankan context due to the dissimilarities in attitudes, beliefs and cultures (Aleassa, Pearson and McClurg, 2011).

Sri Lanka is the fourth country in the Asia-Pacific region that has the highest number of unlicensed software installations (Business Software Alliance [BSA], 2018). However, only a few studies were conducted in Sri Lanka regarding software piracy (Munasinghe and Pamarathna, 2017). Those studies had the limitation of a small sample size, and their focus was limited to ethical and behavioural factors affecting software piracy intention. Thus, the purpose of this study was to address the existing knowledge gap in this context by identifying and investigating behavioural, socio-psychological, ethical, and legal factors affecting software piracy intention among undergraduates in Sri Lanka.

Methodology

The conceptual model was developed (See Figure 1) based on TPB and General Ethics Theory, which were commonly used in previous studies (Arlı and Tjiptono, 2016; Yoon, 2011), yet not used in this context to study software piracy behaviour.

Figure 1: Conceptual Model

Further, knowledge of copyright laws was added as a factor to investigate the legal aspect of software piracy intention based on previous literature (Lau, 2007; Rishi and Mehra, 2017). Six hypotheses were developed based on the findings of the literature reviewed. This study followed the deductive approach and was quantitative in nature.

Undergraduates were selected as the target population based on the finding of previous studies that piracy activities are common among undergraduates (Arli and Tjiptono, 2016; Munasinghe and Pamarathna, 2017; Phau and Ng, 2010; Rishi and Mehra, 2017). This study followed the convenience sampling technique. The minimum recommended sample size was calculated as 97 using a sample size calculator (Soper, 2021). The sample consisted of undergraduates from six state and private universities in Colombo, Sri Lanka. An online questionnaire with pre-validated question items with a 7-point Likert scale was distributed to gather responses. Gathered data was analysed using data analysis software after a data screening. Descriptive data analysis was done using SPSS 27.0 software. Partial Least Square- Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) technique was adopted for Path model analysis using SmartPLS 3.3.3 software.

Results and Discussion

After the data screening, a total of 150 responses were used in the data analysis out of 154 responses received. The majority of respondents were females (57%), while most of the respondents were from the University of Colombo (29.3%). Results showed that most undergraduates use the Internet more than 7 hours per day (52%). Further, results of multiple response questions revealed that 145 respondents have laptop computers and 127 have smartphones that could be used as tools to pirate software.

The results of the measurement model analysis met the relevant criteria to establish the reliability and validity of the research model (Hair et al., 2016). Structural model analysis was conducted to identify the explanatory power of the model and to test the hypotheses (See Table 1). Results revealed that a 45.1% variance in intention was explained by its independent variables. It implied that alternative factors could affect software piracy intention among undergraduates.

Table 1: Hypotheses testing results

	Hypothesis	Path coefficient (β)	P value	Outcome
H1	Knowledge of Copyright Laws -> Intention to Pirate Software Products (-)	0.108	0.080	Not supported
H2	Subjective Norms -> Intention to Pirate Software Products (+)	-0.033	0.666	Not supported
H3	Perceived Behavioural Control -> Intention to Pirate Software Products (+)	0.549	0.000*	Supported
H4	Attitude towards Software Piracy -> Intention to Pirate Software Products (+)	0.188	0.018*	Supported
H5	Moral Obligation -> Attitude towards Software Piracy (-)	-0.381	0.000*	Supported
H6	Perceived Benefits -> Attitude towards Software Piracy (+)	0.228	0.031*	Supported

*Significance at $p < 0.05$

Perceived behavioural control ($\beta= 0.549$, $p= 0.000$) had the most significant positive effect on the intention to pirate software products implying that undergraduates have sufficient skills, opportunities, and resources to engage in software piracy activities. The finding aligned with the previous study findings (Phau and Ng, 2010; Yoon, 2011). Further, the significant positive effect of attitude ($\beta= 0.188$, $p= 0.018$) on intention implied that undergraduates have a positive attitude toward engaging in Software Piracy. However, this result was inconsistent with the findings of Jaafar, Ramayah and Teng (2008). Further, knowledge of copyright laws ($\beta= 0.108$, $p= 0.080$) and subjective norms ($\beta= -0.033$, $p= 0.666$) had a non-significant effect on software piracy intention.

Statistical significance of the negative effect of moral obligation ($\beta= -0.381$, $p= 0.000$) on attitude inferred that undergraduates who perceive software piracy as an unethical activity have negative attitudes toward such activities. Further, perceived benefits ($\beta= 0.228$, $p= 0.031$) had a significant positive effect on attitude, implying that undergraduates perceive pirating software products have more positive outcomes, such as little or no cost, than purchasing and using licensed software. This finding was consistent with the findings of Arli and Tjiptono (2016) and Lau (2007).

Conclusion

This study aimed to identify and investigate the factors affecting software piracy intention among undergraduates. A conceptual model based on TPB and General Ethics Theory was developed to achieve this purpose. According to the study findings, four out of the six hypotheses were supported. Findings further revealed that internal factors such as moral obligation perceived benefits, attitude and perceived behavioural control of an individual have more impact on software piracy intention than external factors such as knowledge of copyright laws and subjective norms (Arli and Tjiptono, 2016). Further, the study findings were useful, to some extent, in bridging the knowledge gap existing related to Software Piracy behaviour among Sri Lankans.

Digital Right Management can be used by software creators to hinder piracy activities (Yoon, 2011). It will help to reduce opportunities to engage in software piracy. Further, higher education institutions must downgrade the unethical, illegal nature and make aware of the negative outcomes of pirating software products among undergraduates to reduce their favourable intention to engage in Software Piracy. The current study only focused on the intention to pirate software products. Thus, future research should investigate the applicability of these factors in other digital media such as music, e-books, and films.

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